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The material-energy nexus in net-zero transition scenarios: exploring environmental trade-offs and uncertainties

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ABSTRACT

As countries pursue net-zero energy systems, material demands intensify. This study develops a framework combining energy system modeling and life cycle assessment to quantify environmental impacts and material needs of energy transition scenarios. We apply it to Switzerland's net-zero scenario, using global sensitivity analysis to assess uncertainties in material intensity, efficiency, and market shares of energy technologies. Results reveal that Switzerland's domestic net-zero goal is met, with life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions decreasing from 40 to 4 megatonnes CO₂-eq between 2020 and 2050. While uncertainties have limited influence on environmental indicators, demand for critical raw materials rises and varies substantially. For instance, lithium demand increases tenfold by 2050, with estimates ranging from 800 to 3,000 tonnes annually. Technological improvements and sub-technology choices, such as lithium-reduced battery chemistries, help mitigate CRM pressures even as storage capacity grows. Findings highlight the need to integrate material considerations into energy planning for sustainable, resilient transitions.

1. Introduction

Climate change represents a global challenge that requires a profound shift towards low-carbon energy technologies (IEA, 2024). Moving away from combustion-based processes involves options like battery electric vehicles, electrification of heat demand in various sectors with technologies like high-temperature heat pumps, and adopting electric motors. This transition, along with the expanded use of renewable energy sources, offers wide-ranging benefits. These benefits span environmental (IPCC, 2023) and public health (Shindell and Smith, 2019) areas and provide economic (Pai et al., 2021) and social (Nature Editorial, 2023) opportunities.

In parallel, the transition to a net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) energy system is anticipated to drive a substantial rise in demand for critical raw materials (CRMs), positioning the energy sector as a major consumer in mineral markets (IEA, 2021). Low-carbon energy systems will necessitate greater quantities and diversity of minerals and metals compared to their fossil fuel-based predecessors (IEA, 2023). As nations and economies strive to reduce emissions, CRMs and competition for their access in enabling sustainable energy transitions draw increasing

attention (Hund et al., 2020; IRENA, 2023; Noailly et al., 2024).

Beyond these supply concerns, the extraction and processing of CRMs generate significant global environmental impacts, including high energy demands and GHG emissions, alongside localized effects such as chemical pollution, water and soil contamination, and ecosystem degradation (Berthet et al., 2024). This emphasizes exploring the material-energy nexus, highlighting the complex relationship between energy systems and material requirements and the need for robust modelling frameworks that help to understand and plan for these resource demands.

Energy system models (ESMs) and integrated assessment models (IAMs) outline potential transformation pathways for the energy transition toward future states achieving specific energy and climate targets (Chang et al., 2021; McLaren and Markusson, 2020). These models predominantly focus on cost- or utility-optimized future scenarios, highlighting, for example, the necessary changes in regional electricity mixes and means of transport to meet global warming mitigation objectives (Riahi et al., 2017). However, while initial efforts have been made to represent material demand within ESMs and IAMs, such frameworks do not yet endogenously incorporate this demand (Schulze

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et al., 2024). Additionally, their representation of broader environmental impacts, such as water use, ecotoxicity, and effects on human health, is limited. As a result, additional tools like life cycle assessment (LCA) are often coupled with these models to provide a more detailed and comprehensive assessment of the different technologies (Vandepaer et al., 2020; Volkart et al., 2018).

Environmental LCA is a complementary tool to comprehensively evaluate the environmental performance of energy technologies and systems. Integrating ESM results into the LCA inventories enables a deeper understanding of potential supply chain-related impacts of different technologies in the energy system. By projecting present-day life cycle inventories into future scenarios –using tools such as the IAM-LCA integration tool *premise* (Sacchi et al., 2022)– it becomes possible to align these inventories with the evolving energy system. This temporal alignment allows for a comprehensive analysis of the sustainability of technologies across different energy system trajectories. This approach supports the creation and analysis of scenarios that address material demand, the interlinkage between energy and resources, and their associated environmental impacts (Harpprecht et al., 2021; van der Meide et al., 2022; C. Zhang et al., 2023).

Conversely, numerous studies in the literature address the overall life-cycle impacts of ESM scenarios. Some have integrated technology-specific LCA coefficients directly into ESMs, allowing for assessments that reflect environmental impacts as scenarios are formulated (Addanki et al., 2024; Rauner and Budzinski, 2017; Vandepaer et al., 2020). Others have applied LCA post-scenario formulation to assess the environmental outcomes of specific model scenarios (Blanco et al., 2020; Hertwich et al., 2015). Regardless of the approach — and despite the current lack of an established methodology or framework for applying LCA at the energy system scenario level (Hahn Menacho et al., 2024), supplementing ESM scenarios with LCA provides valuable insights. It helps measure changes in material demand and the environmental impacts of sourcing these materials due to transitioning from fossil fuels, thereby helping to characterize the material-energy nexus and its broader environmental consequences.

However, assessing energy systems' future material requirements relies on many uncertain input data, such as specific material intensities for each energy technology, technological developments, and market shares of sub-technologies (e.g., specific types of photovoltaic cells or specific battery cell chemistries) and their evolution over time (Schulze et al., 2024). Examples in the literature demonstrate that while some ESMs handle these uncertainties using methods like Monte Carlo simulations (Kalt et al., 2022; S. Wang et al., 2023) and stochastic approaches (Beylot et al., 2019), consistently characterizing the energy scenario and adjusting the environmental impacts of resource sourcing remains a challenge.

In this study, we use LCA to characterize the case of a Swiss net-zero energy transition scenario, providing insights into a developed economy that has pledged to reach net-zero GHG emissions by 2050. By proposing a systematic approach and specific tools to calculate the life-cycle impacts of transition scenarios at a regional scale, we 1) estimate Switzerland's future demand for potentially critical raw materials, 2) evaluate the sensitivity of resource demand to the material intensity factors, future technological developments, and market shares assumed for emerging technologies, and 3) analyze the impacts of such material demand on various environmental impact categories variance. 4) Moreover, we showcase a reproducible and replicable workflow that positions prospective LCA databases along a time dimension to yield a time series of environmental impacts for the energy system.

This framework enables comprehensive, scenario-specific life-cycle impact assessments that can be extended beyond Switzerland to other national or regional contexts, offering a standardized approach for global energy analyses. Additionally, it allows for considering uncertainties in future material needs and their environmental impacts. Through this analysis, we demonstrate how changes in input data for various energy technologies influence their life-cycle impacts. This

provides a robust insight into the broader environmental consequences of material sourcing and the material-energy nexus.

In the following sections, we outline our methodological approach, starting with integrating ESM and LCA in Section 2. Additionally, we detail the study's goal and scope, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and sensitivity analysis. Section 3 presents results from applying this framework to a Swiss net-zero energy transition scenario, highlighting key findings on CRM demand, environmental impacts, and trade-offs and co-benefits across various environmental categories. Section 4 discusses the implications of these findings, the limitations of the current approach, and avenues for future research. Finally, Section 5 concludes by highlighting the importance of comprehensive, resource-conscious planning for sustainable energy transitions.

2. Methods

In this section, we present the steps taken to systematically evaluate the energy system scenario's environmental performance and material demand using LCA. First, we detail the coupling between the ESM and the LCA framework. We then describe the different phases of the LCA as outlined in ISO 14044 (2006), including (1) goal and scope definition, (2) inventory analysis, (3) impact assessment, and (4) interpretation. Within this last phase, we explain the global sensitivity analysis (GSA) conducted to evaluate how uncertainties in the input data influence the results

2.1. Swiss TIMES energy systems model (STEM) and coupling with life cycle assessment (LCA)

This study evaluates a long-term scenario to achieve net-zero territorial CO₂ emissions from Switzerland's fuel combustion and industrial processes by 2050. This scenario, called "SPS1: Team Sprint. Focus on Sustainability" (Panos et al., 2022) and referred to as "Net Zero" hereafter, has been developed within the SURE research project, supported by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy's SWEET program (SFOE, 2020) to help the country meet its net-zero emission target, which has become law (SFOE, 2021). The scenario outlines the necessary steps and energy system configurations to meet this target.

The Swiss TIMES energy systems model (STEM) (Panos et al., 2019), a comprehensive cost-optimization energy system model based on the TIMES framework, provides a solution that aligns with the scenario's objectives and constraints. STEM outputs describe energy production, conversion, and consumption across multiple sectors, identifying the technologies required to meet the net-zero target. The solution produced by STEM involves a portfolio of low-carbon power technologies, the electrification of passenger and freight transport and heating, the capture and storage of hard-to-abate fossil carbon emissions (e.g., from cement production), the use of net negative carbon technologies, such as biomass-based power production with CO₂ capture and storage, and the use of synthetic liquid fuels for the remaining processes still relying on fuel combustion. Fig. 1 summarizes the primary energy consumption and associated CO₂ emissions implied by the *Net Zero* scenario.

First, the soft-coupling tool *premise* (Sacchi et al., 2022) aligns life cycle inventories with STEM's results and ensures consistency in representing the Swiss energy system and its global interactions. As developed by Hahn Menacho et al. (2024), processes occurring within Switzerland and involving primary, secondary, and final energy carriers are updated throughout the LCA database in alignment with the projections of the STEM scenario. Each variable representing energy conversion, transmission, distribution, and consumption within the STEM framework is linked to an LCA dataset, with detailed mapping in the SI document (SI1, S8). Altogether, 203 STEM processes that produce or consume energy are mapped to the LCA database, encompassing final energy uses such as fossil fuels, electricity, and hydrogen used in transport, industrial and residential heat, and other industrial and service activities. The efficiencies of secondary energy conversion

Fig. 1. Primary energy consumption and CO₂ emissions for Switzerland according to the Net Zero scenario evaluated. Primary energy consumption includes the total energy demand of all energy carriers, such as the energy used directly by end-users and conversion losses in processes like thermal storage and electro-fuel synthesis. The ambient heat retrieved by heat pumps is counted as energy supply. The category "Other" includes the variables contributing less than 5 % of the total. Detailed scenario outputs are available in the Supplementary Information material (SI1, S7). In-depth descriptions of the STEM model and the evaluated scenario can be found in Panos et al. (2023) and Panos et al. (2025), respectively.

processes, such as heat and power plants, are also adjusted in the LCA database to align with those assumed in STEM.

Processes located outside of Switzerland that directly and indirectly support the Swiss energy system (e.g., import of fuels, electricity, etc.) are also temporally adjusted using the global IAM scenario from REMIND (Luderer et al., 2015) under the SSP2-PkBudg1150 scenario. This scenario aims to limit global warming to approximately 2 °C compared to pre-industrial levels, with a worldwide carbon budget of 1150 gigatonnes of CO₂ for this century. Employing such a global scenario ensures consistency between the sectoral changes introduced by the Swiss *Net Zero* scenario domestically and those abroad, ensuring that the decarbonization of material and energy commodity production for Swiss imports occurs at a similar pace. The output is a data package containing the STEM scenario data, adjusted life cycle inventories, and related mapping and metadata information.

Second, the Python package *pathways* (Sacchi and Hahn-Menacho, 2024) reads the data package produced by *premise* and calculates the overall life-cycle impacts of the scenario for each time step. Results are broken down by environmental indicator, product or service consumer, process category, geographical location of the consumer, geographical origin of impacts, and time step. As noted in Hahn Menacho et al. (2024), *pathways* addresses the issue of double-counting impacts in LCA supply chains by eliminating the contribution of final energy carriers within the supply chains of other final energy carriers. For example, when calculating the environmental impact of battery electric trucks, *pathways* ensures that emissions from diesel-powered trucks are not included in the electricity supply chain that powers them, and vice versa. Access to the data package and the scripts used to produce the results in this study can be found in the Supplementary Information document (SI1, S5, and S8).

2.2. Life cycle assessment (LCA)

2.2.1. Goal and scope

This study aims to quantify the life-cycle environmental impacts and material demands of Switzerland's *Net Zero* energy scenario. We define the functional unit as the production, consumption, and supply of final energy in Switzerland to satisfy the system energy demand from 2020 to 2050. This includes the necessary infrastructure for energy supply and usage. For example, the demand for a unit of energy stored in a stationary battery would be linked to the electricity grid demand, maintenance and losses, auxiliary components, and charging infrastructure.

Final energy consumers in the STEM model fall into four economic

sectors: transport, industry, service, and residential. Each subsector is further split by the type of energy carrier used and the technology employed (e.g., "Industry|Electricity|Electric boiler", "Industry|Electricity|Heat pump", etc.). The datasets used for each final energy consumer that constitute the functional unit set are available in the Supplementary Information (SI1, S5, and S8).

2.2.2. Life cycle inventory (LCI)

The ecoinvent LCA database v3.10 (system model "allocation, cut-off by classification") is used as the primary source of background data (Wernet et al., 2016), further modified by *premise* to align inventories and technology shares with the STEM scenario.

Additionally, *premise* enhances the database by including inventories for emerging technologies relevant to the energy system that are linked to important material requirements. These include, amongst others: perovskite (Roffeis et al., 2022) and gallium arsenide (Pallas et al., 2020) photovoltaic cells; sodium-ion (S. Zhang et al., 2024), lithium-sulfur (Wickerts et al., 2023), lithium-air (F. Wang et al., 2020), and vanadium redox-flow batteries (Weber et al., 2018); and, proton exchange membrane and alkaline electrolyzers (Gerloff, 2021).

Regarding the co-production of metals in mining processes, we modify the database to allocate the amounts of metals extracted according to physical mass balances: extraction of individual elements in the ore is fully attributed to the production of the respective metal; while other elementary and intermediate flows such as electricity and diesel remain unchanged and follow an economic allocation (SI1, S9), which is also the default option to deal with multi-functionality in ecoinvent (Wernet et al., 2016). As discussed by Berger et al. (2020), this approach ensures a correct mass balance.

2.2.3. Material requirements and uncertainty

Current LCI databases inadequately represent potentially scarce raw materials, particularly those used in small quantities, such as platinum group metals (PGMs) and rare earth oxides. To fill this gap, we build on the research by Schlichenmaier & Naegler (2022) and gather additional data on the material requirements for various technologies. These technologies include wind turbines, electric and internal combustion engine vehicles, photovoltaic panels, concentrated solar power plants, nuclear plants, electric batteries (both mobile and stationary), fuel cells, and electrolyzers.

We use the collected data to create probability distributions of each technology's current and future material intensities. These probability distributions represent generalized global trends, as we do not add

regional granularity to the material intensities in this study. Most of these probability distributions are triangular because this approach is well-suited for limited data availability, relying on known minimum, maximum, and most likely values to approximate variability. The median value in the literature serves as the mode, with the lowest and highest values being the boundaries. The Supplementary Information (SI1, S2; and SI2) provides detailed data, distribution parameters, and references.

Moreover, probability distributions are employed to represent the uncertainty surrounding future technological efficiency, such as the lifespan and conversion efficiency of electrolyzers, the module efficiency of photovoltaic panels, and the energy density of battery cells—all of which significantly impact the demand for material resources. The distributions characterizing the uncertainty around the efficiency of technologies and the energy density of battery cells can be found in the Supplementary Information (SI1, S3-S5).

Finally, the uncertainty regarding the market shares of future technologies is also accounted for. An algorithm generates pseudo-random market shares for each group of competing technologies from 2020 to 2050 (e.g., gearbox versus direct-drive wind turbines), ensuring that these shares fall within anticipated intervals and collectively sum to 100%. The Supplementary Information (SI1, S1) details the expected market share intervals.

The uncertainty in material requirements, combined with that surrounding technological efficiency and market shares, forms the basis of the input data used in the Monte Carlo simulations and GSA performed in this study – further detailed in Section 2.2.5. Fig. 2 illustrates the implementation of such probability distributions along the electricity

supply chain for battery-electric passenger cars.

2.2.4. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)

We select eight key environmental impact categories to evaluate the environmental sustainability of the energy system scenario. These categories are chosen to capture the multidimensional aspects of environmental sustainability in the context of the energy-material nexus. We assess (1) climate change impacts, using the global warming potential (GWP) over a 100-year time horizon (Andreasi Bassi et al., 2023); (2) particulate matter formation potential, linked to human health impacts (Huijbregts et al., 2017); (3) acidification, to evaluate the impact of acidifying substances deposit (EPLCA, 2022); (4) freshwater ecotoxicity, evaluating emissions harmful to freshwater ecosystems (Huijbregts et al., 2017); (5) land use, quantifying total land area (all types) occupied over time; and, (6) net fresh water use, defined as the difference between freshwater abstraction and release. Additionally, we evaluate mineral resource depletion using two indicators: (7) crustal scarcity, a scarcity-weighted minerals demand indicator that uses crustal concentrations as a proxy for long-term global elemental scarcity (Arvidsson et al., 2020); and (8) abiotic resource depletion for elements, where present production and reserves of individual elements are combined to measure the scarcity of the resources (van Oers et al., 2020). Finally, we report the physical annual demand for 64 metals classified as critical based on assessments from major international reports (Grohol and Veeh, 2023; Moreira and Laing, 2022) and scientific literature (Schlichenmaier and Naegler, 2022).

Fig. 2. System boundaries and uncertainties are considered along the supply of one megajoule of final energy to the final consumer (i.e., a battery electric passenger car). System boundaries include the production, supply and use of final energy, but also the infrastructure needed to use it (e.g., grid, battery, electric motor, etc.). Infrastructures unaffected by a change in the energy carrier are omitted (e.g., the car chassis, road, etc.). In this example, the capacity of the onboard battery varies from 30 to 80 kilowatt-hour (and is further normalized to one megajoule of electricity consumed by the vehicle). Several battery technologies compete to provide storage capacity, each associated with a probability distribution for the market share (specific to a year). Market share uncertainty values within the same market always sum to 100% for each Monte Carlo iteration. Each battery technology is associated with a probability distribution regarding the cell energy density, which also improves over time. At the electricity production level, within the scenario-defined technologies (e.g., photovoltaic panels), sub-technologies compete to supply electricity based on market shares associated with probability distributions. Each technology is also associated with probability distributions regarding material use. Efficiency and material use boundary values usually change over time as well. In the case of photovoltaic panels, the module efficiency determines the panel surface needed to reach the reference power output.

2.2.5. Interpretation and global sensitivity analysis (GSA)

GSA quantifies the contribution of each input uncertainty to the total variability in the model outputs (Saltelli, 2002). This method helps us understand how distinct sources of uncertainty can affect the various environmental and resource indicators, including metal demands. This study explicitly targets uncertainties related to material and metal intensities, technological advancements, and the market penetration of energy-related sub-technologies, as explained in earlier Section 2.2.3. STEM does not provide uncertainty estimates, so none are included in our analysis. Other sources of uncertainty are deliberately excluded. For example, we do not consider uncertainty data included in the process inventories of the ecoinvent LCA database.

Uncertainty distributions are applied to three key areas: 1) 500 inventory exchanges related to using material resources within technologies, 2) 103 inventory exchanges reflecting variations in the lifespan, use, and efficiency of energy technologies, and 3) 36 inventory exchanges representing sub-technology market shares. These distributions are based on various model parameters detailed in the Supplementary Information (SI1, S1–5). All other exchange values in the LCA database are constant over time or modified according to the *Net Zero* scenario. The uncertainties are then propagated through Monte Carlo simulations. We report the 5th, 50th, and 95th percentile values of the resulting Monte Carlo distribution for each environmental and material indicator described in Section 2.2.4.

To identify the most influential parameters driving output variability, we use the delta moment-independent method (DMIM). Originally introduced by Borgonovo (2007), DMIM provides a robust framework independent of the sampling generation technique (Plischke et al., 2013) and has been previously applied in LCA contexts (Kim et al., 2022a,b). Delta indices assigned to each parameter range from 0 to 1, where higher values indicate a stronger influence on the output distribution. To ensure the robustness of our results, we conducted preliminary tests to determine the optimal number of Monte Carlo iterations, ultimately setting the iteration count to 2000 to achieve convergence.

It is important to emphasize that the variability in the distribution of results presented in the following sections arises solely from uncertainties within the supply chain of technologies relevant to the demand for CRMs. The scenarios generated by STEM are exploratory in nature. Multiple technological pathways and strategies can achieve net-zero GHG emissions, and the scenario used here represents just one possible approach, minimizing system costs based on a specific set of deterministic model input parameters. As a result, significant sources of uncertainty that could significantly impact GHG emissions and other environmental indicators are not accounted for in this analysis to single out the uncertainty that arises from CRM-demanding technologies.

3. Results

This section presents the material and environmental implications of Switzerland's net-zero transition. First, we examine how the increasing adoption of low-carbon technologies affects CRM demand. Next, we analyze the environmental impacts of the transition scenario, highlighting key trade-offs and co-benefits across multiple impact categories.

3.1. Material demand

The transition to a low-carbon energy system in Switzerland drives significant shifts in the demand for CRMs. This is caused by the growing adoption of electric vehicles (EVs), renewable energy storage technologies, and other low-carbon infrastructure. Below, we detail these trends, focusing on key materials shaping this transition.

3.1.1. Lithium and battery metals

Lithium demand increases substantially as EVs and battery storage systems become central to the energy transition scenario. As illustrated

in Fig. 3, the median annual lithium demand rises from 250 tonnes in 2020 to 2000 tonnes by 2050, with a broader range of uncertainty extending from 800 to over 3000 tonnes. This variability is driven by market shares of different battery chemistries, material intensity, and technological advancements. Sodium-ion batteries, for example, offer a lithium-free alternative. The exact trajectory of these market share shifts will depend on various factors, including technological advancements, cost reductions, and policy incentives, all of which influence the adoption rates of competing battery technologies. In our model, the projected shares of different battery chemistries are determined using probability distributions that reflect anticipated intervals for market shares (SI1, S1). Importantly, the uncertainty range widens over time, as 2020 market shares are based on current observed values with no associated variability, whereas future years incorporate broader probability distributions.

While market share-related uncertainty alone accounts for a variance in lithium demand of -46% to $+37\%$ (pink error bars in Fig. 3), these do not capture the full range of the spread. When additional factors such as battery energy density and storage capacity are included, the variance widens from -54% to $+77\%$ (black error bars). Furthermore, although the overall demand for EVs and battery systems continues to increase, this growth rate slows over time due to anticipated improvements in battery energy density and material efficiency, which mitigate the need for even larger material requirements. These assumptions are built into the probability distributions applied to material intensities and technological advancements (SI1, S2-S5). As highlighted by the GSA (Fig. 5 and SI1, S6), described in Section 2.2.5, the electricity storage capacity of future batteries is identified as the main parameter influencing this variance.

Similar trends are observed in other key battery metals, such as cobalt and vanadium. Vanadium demand rises sharply from 0.9 tonnes in 2020 to a median of 156 tonnes by 2050, with uncertainty extending from 35 tonnes to 289 tonnes. Low-lithium alternatives, such as vanadium redox-flow batteries for stationary energy storage, mitigate lithium dependence but increase reliance on vanadium. Beyond battery applications, vanadium is critical for high-strength steel alloys, which in our model are used in wind turbines, further contributing to increased vanadium demand. This illustrates how efforts to minimize reliance on one critical material may inadvertently increase dependency on another, underscoring the need for quantifying such consequences and a balanced approach to material management in the energy transition.

3.1.2. Platinum group metals (PGMs)

The transition scenario profoundly affects the demand for PGMs like platinum and palladium. As the automotive industry shifts toward battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and hydrogen-based technologies, the need for platinum in catalytic converters for internal combustion engines diminishes. By 2040, platinum demand is projected to decline to approximately 540 kilograms, representing just 30% of its 2020 level. However, by 2050, demand partially rebounds to around 700 kilograms, fueled by its growing use in electrolyzers and fuel cells, essential for supporting a green hydrogen economy.

Iridium demand, on the other hand, rises from negligible levels in 2020 to about 80 kilograms by 2050, reflecting its critical role in proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers and fuel cells, which are essential for hydrogen production and storage. These trends underscore the complex interplay between declining conventional technology uses and new, emerging needs in low-carbon systems.

3.1.3. Materials for renewable energy technologies

Renewable energy technologies also drive significant CRM demand. For instance, gallium, a key component in certain photovoltaic sub-technologies such as copper indium gallium selenide (CIGS) and gallium arsenide (GaAs) solar cells, experiences a marked increase in demand from 2.5 tonnes in 2020 to a median of nearly 40 tonnes by 2050. Variability in gallium demand, ranging from 20 tonnes to over 50

Fig. 3. Annual life-cycle material demand per final energy consumer category for Switzerland’s Net Zero scenario. Pink error bars indicate the range between the 5th and 95th percentiles, considering only variations in projected technology market shares, with red dots marking the median. Black error bars show the range between the 5th and 95th percentiles when all sources of uncertainty are considered, with black dots representing the median. Note that median marks from both distributions do not necessarily align. Detailed results for 64 elements are available in the Supplementary Information (SI2, S6). Pie charts show the contribution shares of the final energy processes and sectors, respectively, to the total demand for each material. Individual processes contributing less than 5 % are aggregated under “Other”.

tonnes, is largely driven by the market share of competing photovoltaic technologies. At the lower end, increased deployment of cadmium telluride (CdTe) cells, which do not use gallium, drives demand down; while at the higher end, the widespread adoption of CIGS and GaAs significantly raises gallium demand. Crystalline silicon (c-Si) technologies also contribute to the demand for gallium, although to a lesser extent than CIGS and GaAs. This underscores how selecting specific photovoltaic sub-technologies may heavily influence the demand for certain CRMs, emphasizing the need for strategic decisions to ensure

material availability for the successful upscaling of solar energy. Similarly, silver, though not currently classified as CRM by entities such as the European Union, experiences a fourfold demand increase from 17 to 66 tonnes by 2050, mainly due to its role in photovoltaic panels and electrolyzers.

Wind turbines, another cornerstone of renewable energy deployment, significantly impact the demand for rare earth elements like neodymium, dysprosium, and praseodymium. Neodymium, crucial for producing permanent magnets used in wind turbine generators,

experiences a more than 300 % increase in demand as wind energy capacity expands, rising from 5 tonnes in 2020 to an estimated 17 tonnes by 2050. The variance in neodymium demand is influenced by the material intensity of different wind turbine designs and the choice between direct-drive versus gearbox turbines. Direct-drive turbines require approximately 10 times more rare earth elements than gearbox turbines. According to the GSA (Fig. 5 and SI1-S6), neodymium oxide requirements in onshore gearbox wind turbines, driven by their greater market share, emerge as the model's most influential uncertain parameter for neodymium extraction, with a variance of -26% to $+28\%$ by 2050.

3.1.4. Materials for the mining and refining sectors

The mining and refining sectors exemplify the interconnected nature of material supply and energy transitions. Sulfur, predominantly used in upstream activities as sulfuric acid in refining various materials, sees its demand increase from 30 to 70 kilotonnes between 2020 and 2050. This increase is directly tied to the rising need for refined metals to support the energy transition. Although sulfur is not scarce and does not currently face significant supply risks, it holds great economic importance, and its price has shown considerable volatility in recent decades (Blengini et al., 2020).

Despite its abundance, sulfur's supply is intricately linked to the fossil fuel industry, as it is often produced as a byproduct of natural gas and petroleum refining, with few discretionary sources available (ecoinvent, 2023; Wagenfeld et al., 2019). As fossil fuel extraction decreases, ensuring a stable sulfur supply may become increasingly critical for refining metals needed in low-carbon energy systems. Conversely, the decline in barium demand (SI1-S6, Fig. 8), mainly used in oil and gas drilling (ecoinvent, 2023; USGS, 2023), highlights the shifting priorities of the energy sector away from fossil fuels.

The interconnectedness between sulfur supply and fossil fuel production highlights potential resource availability and supply challenges as energy systems evolve. This aligns with the insights of Månberger (2021), which discusses the trade-offs associated with reduced fossil fuel use and its impact on the supply of critical resources. This highlights the importance of developing integrated models to anticipate potential barriers and ensure an effective transition to a sustainable energy future.

3.2. Environmental impacts

Shifting the focus to environmental impacts, the transition to a net-zero energy system significantly reduces GHG emissions in Switzerland. Life-cycle GHG emissions drop from 40 to 4 megatonnes per year between 2020 and 2050, as shown in Fig. 4. This reduction aligns with domestic net-zero emissions, with the remaining emissions attributed to upstream activities abroad. In 2020, the uncertainty range for GHG emissions, represented by the percentage change between the median and the 5th and 95th percentiles, is within $\pm 0.5\%$. By 2050, as varying parameters become more relevant, this range expands to $\pm 10\%$, driven primarily by uncertainty in EV battery storage capacity. The dominance of battery storage capacity as the most influential parameter reflects its direct, linear relationship with total EV battery demand in a scenario heavily reliant on electrification. The broad triangular distribution applied (min-max: 30–80 kWh, mode 48 kWh) further amplifies its influence across multiple impact categories.

Reducing GHG emissions comes with co-benefits, including decreases in particulate matter formation and acidification. However, trade-offs emerge in other environmental categories. Freshwater ecotoxicity increases by 40 % ($\pm 9\%$), primarily due to the material demand for EV batteries. Similarly, land use impacts, measured as the total area occupied over time to meet the final energy demand of the system, also

Fig. 4. Annual environmental life-cycle impacts per final energy consumer category for Switzerland's Net Zero scenario. Pink error bars indicate the range between the 5th and 95th percentiles, considering only variations in projected technology market shares, with red dots marking the median. Black error bars show the range between the 5th and 95th percentiles when all sources of uncertainty are considered, with black dots representing the median. Note that median marks from both distributions do not necessarily align. Impact categories include (1) global warming potential, measured in megatonnes of CO₂-eq; (2) particulate matter formation, in kilotonnes of PM_{2.5}-eq; (3) acidification, in million mol H⁺-eq; (4) ecotoxicity, in billion comparative toxic units; (5) land use, in square kilometer-year; (6) water use – comprises the abstraction of freshwater – in cubic kilometers; (7) crustal scarcity, in gigatonnes of silicon-eq; and (8) abiotic depletion, in tonnes of antimony-eq.

rise as the deployment of bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) expands, increasing the need for managed forest land. Despite this increase, uncertainties around land use impacts remain limited ($\pm 2\%$), as the analysis primarily focuses on uncertainties related to metal and material consumption rather than land-use management or shifts in afforestation rates.

Resource depletion indicators, which are most influenced by the uncertainties considered in this study, show mixed trends. Interestingly, the crustal scarcity indicator, a proxy for long-term global elemental scarcity based on crustal concentrations, remains roughly constant, decreasing from 5 to 4.7 gigatonnes of silicon-equivalent between 2020 and 2050. This indicator, which heavily weighs the scarcity of PGMs, declines as demand for platinum and palladium in internal combustion engines and exhaust systems phases out to bounce back again to its initial level in 2050. Meanwhile, its variability is primarily driven by the emerging use of iridium in electrolyzers, with fluctuations of ± 1.6 gigatonnes. Conversely, the abiotic depletion indicator for elements, which focuses on current production and reserves of minerals and metals and excludes fossil fuel resources, rises significantly from 255 to 601 tonnes of antimony-equivalent (-17% , $+20\%$) between 2020 and 2050. The variability in this indicator is influenced by a broader range of parameters, reflecting the diverse material demands of renewable

energy and storage technologies.

4. Discussion

This section contextualizes the study’s findings, highlighting key implications for energy transition planning and CRM sustainability. The first part (Section 4.1) examines the importance of integrating life-cycle thinking into transition scenarios and the role of technological choices in shaping material demand and environmental impacts. It also discusses the broader strategic and policy implications of our findings. The second part (Section 4.2) outlines the study’s limitations and potential directions for future research, emphasizing opportunities to refine methodological approaches and broaden the scope of analysis.

4.1. Key findings and implications

The findings of this study underscore the critical importance of adopting a holistic perspective when designing and implementing energy transition policies. First, life-cycle impacts must be considered to ensure that transition scenarios effectively reduce environmental burdens. While decarbonization efforts focus on reducing GHG emissions, our results highlight the need to reflect a broader array of environmental

Fig. 5. Heatmap of delta indices from a moment-independent GSA, highlighting the most influential uncertain parameters across key life-cycle environmental impact categories. Rows represent the parameters, and columns represent the impact categories. For each category, only parameters with a normalized delta value above 90% are shown, and the exact indices are annotated within each cell. This sensitivity index, ranging from 0 to 1, quantifies the degree to which each parameter influences the variability of the output distribution, with higher values indicating a stronger influence on the respective environmental categories.

impacts, such as particulate matter formation, water use, and resource depletion, to evaluate the co-benefits and trade-offs associated with reducing climate impacts and the general feasibility of transition pathways.

Secondly, the comprehensive evaluation of sub-technologies and material intensities within the energy-material nexus is crucial. Neglecting to account for the full spectrum of sub-technologies and material requirements could lead to unforeseen bottlenecks or hidden impacts, potentially compromising the feasibility and effectiveness of energy transition scenarios. While ESMs and IAMs project broad technology deployments, such as total photovoltaic or wind capacities, they often overlook the detailed differences in material needs and effects on different impact categories that LCA can provide. This level of detail is valuable, as our study suggests that while the specific selection of sub-technologies might not significantly impact the achievement of decarbonization targets, it substantially affects other environmental impacts and CRM demand.

Furthermore, the GSA results highlight the factors in our model driving uncertainty in both material and environmental impacts, offering a valuable understanding for future research and mitigation efforts. Delta indices in the GSA (ranging from 0 to 1 by definition) reflect the degree to which each parameter contributes to the variability of the output distributions, with higher values indicating stronger influence across one or more environmental categories. As shown in Fig. 5, electricity storage capacity in electric vehicles emerges in the evaluated Swiss scenario as the dominant factor affecting several environmental categories, including GWP, particulate matter formation, acidification, and demand for CRMs. This underscores the strong influence of battery technologies on shaping environmental outcomes in the scenario. Addressing this uncertainty requires prioritizing research and development in high energy-density, low-impact battery technologies, exploring alternative chemistries such as sodium-ion batteries, and improving recycling rates to reduce reliance on CRMs such as lithium and cobalt.

While the influence of other specific products and processes is often confined to single material demands, some cases are particularly significant. For instance, iridium demand is driven by its use in PEM electrolyzers, highlighting the need for advancements in catalyst efficiency or alternative materials to support hydrogen production. Similarly, the demand for platinum in internal combustion engine vehicles reflects the effects of accelerating the phase-out of these technologies. Neodymium demand, driven by its use in wind turbines, calls for further exploration of rare earth element recycling and alternative magnet technologies to support wind energy expansion. By revealing these critical sensitivities, the GSA pinpoints areas where technological advancements, material substitutions, or policy interventions could have the greatest impact in reducing uncertainties and optimizing system sustainability. Ultimately, Fig. 5 serves as a guide for identifying which parameters deserve the most attention and development to ensure the robustness of future energy transition strategies.

Finally, while this study primarily aims to develop a structured approach to identifying potential material bottlenecks and environmental trade-offs in net-zero energy transitions at the scenario level, our findings also carry strategic and policy implications. First, demand for a broad range of CRMs is projected to increase substantially – while their supply chains, particularly from a Swiss and European perspective, remain exposed to geopolitical and economic risks. Hence, mitigation strategies will be essential and may include diversification of primary material supply, domestic CRM production and refining, and establishment of recycling infrastructure to supplement primary sources with secondary sources (Grohol and Veeh, 2023; Noailly et al., 2024). Second, demand for certain CRMs is largely concentrated in a few key technologies or sectors, such as iridium in PEM electrolyzers and lithium and cobalt in electric vehicle batteries. For this reason, early investments in research and development of alternative technologies are critical for long-term resource security. Finally, diversifying the renewable energy mix is not only essential to ensure a reliable energy supply but can also

help mitigate CRM supply risks and environmental trade-offs. Given the uneven distribution of renewable resources and the interdependencies in CRM supply chains, fostering international cooperation will be necessary for a diversified energy supply and to secure sustainable material flows for the energy transition (Noailly et al., 2024).

4.2. Limitations and outlook

While this study provides valuable insights into the material-energy nexus, several areas for improvement and opportunities for future work are identified. One such limitation concerns mining practices and recycling rates. The analysis assumes that current practices in material extraction and recycling remain unchanged, potentially overlooking advancements in these areas and leading to overestimating material extraction and associated environmental burdens. However, the framework developed in this study offers opportunities to evaluate emerging strategies for improving the sustainability of CRM supply chains. Responsible mining practices, including strategies for managing mine tailings and adopting circular economy principles, are increasingly recognized as essential to reducing the environmental footprint of primary raw material extraction (Kinnunen et al., 2022). These practices could be modeled by incorporating updated life cycle inventories that reflect advancements in mining technologies and more sustainable operational practices. Similarly, integrating urban mining into the material-energy nexus could shift the focus from natural resource exploitation to anthropogenic resource recovery, offering dual benefits: recovering valuable materials and mitigating waste generation through circularity-based alternatives (Xavier et al., 2023). Evaluating the impact of circular economy policies, such as CRM tracking, recycling guidelines and policies, and restrictions on the export of CRM-containing waste, could also provide insights into reducing environmental impacts while supporting resource security (Lehtimäki et al., 2024; Vafeas et al., 2024). These advancements could be effectively integrated into the framework by introducing scenarios that reflect enhanced recycling rates, improved resource management, and circular economy initiatives. However, as material demand exhibits substantial growth rates, recycling will, in any case, only provide limited shares of material demand. Thus, we consider this limitation in our work to be of minor importance.

Addressing the spatial heterogeneity of environmental impacts is equally critical. The study lacks detailed regionalization of environmental impacts, which is particularly important for categories such as water use, biodiversity, and particulate matter formation, especially in the mining sector (Cabernard and Pfister, 2022; Northey et al., 2018). For instance, water requirements previously driven by cooling in combustion-based processes may shift to mining regions to support mineral extraction for renewable technologies, while particulate matter pollution—formerly concentrated in urban areas from combustion vehicles—is expected to increasingly affect mining zones as electric vehicle production scales up (Hahn Menacho et al., 2024). Enhancing the spatial resolution of these impacts would provide a more accurate assessment of the environmental consequences of materials extraction and processing, allowing for more targeted and effective policy interventions.

A further opportunity lies in improving the granularity of material assessments in energy transition scenarios by integrating LCA with Material Flow Analysis (MFA). Currently, the demand for materials is linearized, i.e., evenly distributed over the entire lifetime of each infrastructure component due to the nature of LCA, smoothing out peaks and troughs. Although this approach preserves cumulative material demand, it does not accurately reflect the temporal dynamics caused by the installation, operation, and decommissioning phases—information usually provided by ESMs and IAMs. For instance, demand for tungsten, primarily used in our model in nuclear energy as tungsten carbide, decreases gradually over time (SI1, S6-Figure 8). However, under the current policy framework, with no new nuclear power plants projected

and the planned decommissioning of existing ones, tungsten demand is expected to drop sharply rather than taper off gradually. Similarly, for emerging technologies like photovoltaics, the bulk of material demand occurs during installation rather than evenly distributed across the technology's operational lifetime. By coupling MFA and LCA, future studies could offer a more dynamic and detailed understanding of material flows, better capturing the complexities of the energy transition and its resource implications (Barkhausen et al., 2023). Extending this framework to model material flows endogenously would allow LCA results to inform MFA, while MFA outputs could, in turn, refine the LCI in a consistent and coherent manner. This integration would enable a more detailed representation of short-term surges and supply chain constraints while also accounting for future recycling rates based on material availability.

In addition, the study highlights the need for improved indicators to assess resource depletion in the context of prospective LCA. The crustal scarcity indicator, for example, emphasizes the scarcity of PGMs, which could be misleading when interpreting the overall resource demand, as this indicator suggests a decreasing need for scarce materials in our case study. Similarly, the abiotic resource depletion indicator may not fully align with the goals of prospective LCA since it relies on current production and reserve data to project future resource availability. To address these shortcomings, future research should explore the integration of emerging criticality indicators, such as SPOTTER (Berr et al., 2022) or GeoPolRisk (Santillán-Saldivar et al., 2021), into the prospective LCA framework. These indicators could provide more accurate insights into the potential risks and vulnerabilities associated with CRM supply chains, supporting more informed decision-making in the energy transition.

Finally, a comparison with similar studies, such as García-Gusano et al. (2025), which evaluates CRM needs under Spain's prospective electricity generation mix, reinforces the broader relevance of these findings. Their low-carbon scenario, characterized by ambitious electrification via high EV penetration, heat pumps, and large-scale adoption of wind and photovoltaic technologies, also reveals significant increases in CRM demand compared to business-as-usual scenarios. Like our results, their study highlights substantial growth in the demand for metals associated with the low-carbon technologies used for decarbonization, underscoring the shared material challenges of electrification-focused net-zero transitions. Future research should focus on validating these findings through alternative scenarios. Alternative pathways could reach the net-zero goal in other ways, for example, by employing more carbon dioxide removal or more low-carbon synthetic fuels instead of direct electrification. Extending the scenario space will allow for a more dynamic and nuanced understanding of material demands over time.

5. Conclusion

This study develops an integrated framework combining LCA with ESM to quantify the life-cycle environmental impacts and CRM demand of energy transition scenarios. By systematically combining LCA with ESM, the framework enables a comprehensive assessment of how emerging energy technologies and sub-technology choices shape future resource demand and environmental outcomes.

We apply this approach to assess Switzerland's material-energy nexus within a net-zero transition scenario. We estimated Switzerland's future CRM demand, revealing substantial increases in materials like lithium and vanadium primarily driven by EV and battery storage adoption, and highlighted the sensitivity of these projections to shifts in technology market shares and material intensities. GSA further identifies key drivers of uncertainty, such as electricity storage capacity in EVs, which strongly influence both material demand and environmental impacts. Furthermore, we developed a flexible and reproducible workflow that allows for scenario-specific life-cycle impact assessments. This workflow can be extended to other national contexts, providing a

versatile tool for global energy analyses that consider a broad range of environmental impacts and material demand.

The Swiss case study offers valuable insights not only for Switzerland but for all countries that need to scale up renewable energy installations and electrify their energy systems. Such countries, especially those lacking significant hydropower capacity, are very likely to face enormous material demand increases and some environmental trade-offs as they deploy more photovoltaic and wind power installations and additional stationary battery storage. At the same time, they stand to benefit from substantial environmental co-benefits. The framework developed in this study provides a structured approach to be applied beyond Switzerland to quantify material demands, evaluate trade-offs, and identify technology options that can reduce reliance on specific CRMs, alleviate supply chain pressures, and enhance the resilience of energy systems.

Several novel findings emerge from this analysis regarding the role of uncertainties, particularly concerning the sensitivity of CRM demand to sub-technology selection within energy systems – a level of granularity often overlooked in ESMs and IAMs. First, the uncertainties evaluated in this study have limited influence on decarbonization targets. These uncertainties have a more pronounced effect on other environmental impacts, such as freshwater use and ecotoxicity, but their overall impact remains constrained. Second, sub-technology choices, such as battery chemistries or photovoltaic sub-technologies, strongly influence CRM demand profiles, significantly defining reliance on specific materials like lithium, cobalt, and rare earth elements. This creates opportunities to alleviate material pressures through strategic technology prioritization. However, such prioritization must be carefully balanced, as focusing on one technology can shift pressures to the demand curves of other critical materials, underscoring the interconnected nature of CRM supply chains in the energy transition. Finally, the parameters governing technology performance, such as material intensities and efficiencies, exhibit substantial leverage to curb CRM demand even as the overall adoption of low-carbon technologies continues to grow.

In conclusion, a holistic approach to energy transition planning is essential. This study's integrated workflow offers stakeholders a robust tool to assess decarbonization goals and CRM needs, ensuring that the transition to low-carbon energy systems achieves emissions reductions and considers long-term resource sustainability. These insights serve as a reference for policymakers and researchers aiming to navigate the complex landscape of energy transitions, emphasizing data-driven, resource-conscious planning.

Glossary

- CRM: Critical Raw Material
- ESM: Energy System Model
- GHG: Greenhouse Gas
- GSA: Global Sensitivity Analysis
- IAM: Integrated Assessment Model
- LCA: Life Cycle Assessment
- PGM: Platinum Group Metals
- STEM: Swiss TIMES Energy Model
- TIMES: The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alvaro J. Hahn Menacho: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Romain Sacchi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Christian Bauer:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Evangelos Panos:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Russell McKenna:** Writing – review & editing. **Peter Burgherr:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

The code required to reproduce the results presented in this study, and the results themselves, can be found in the repository indicated in SI1

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